

CONSTRAINTS FACED BY THE DATE PALM GROWERS OF KUTCH DISTRICT AND THEIR SUGGESTIONS TO OVERCOME THE CONSTRAINTS IN ADOPTION OF THE DATE PALM PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY

R. J. Patel¹, R. R. Prajapati², K. V. Chaudhary³

1 Ph. D. Scholar, Dept. of Agricultural Extension and Communication, CPCA, SDAU, Sardarkrushinagar – 385506

2. Associate Professor, College of Agriculture, SDAU, Tharad- 385575

3. Assistant Professor, KIASRC, Uka Tarsadiya University, Bardoli, Surat – 394350

Email: roshanipatel582@gmail.com

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Abstract

Date palm (Phoenix dactylifera L.) is one of the oldest cultivated horticultural crops of the world. Date palm is one of the important arid fruit crops of Gujarat and very popularly known as 'Kalpavruksh of Kutch'. The present study was conducted in Kutch district of Gujarat state as the district ranks first so far the area and production under date palm is concerned. Four talukas viz., Mundra, Anjar, Mandvi and Bhuj were selected purposively as they occupy more than 90 per cent area of date palm in the district. Five villages having date palm cultivation were selected randomly. A list of farmers cultivating date palm since last three years was prepared. From the village wise list, twelve farmers were randomly selected to make a sample size of 240 date palm growers. Ex-post facto research design was used for the study. Major constraints faced by the date palm growers were; lack of knowledge about value added products of date palm (87.50%), unawareness about export system (86.67%), non remunerative price (85.83%) and complicated method for loan and subsidies (85.42%). Major suggestions they provided were; literature about scientific methods of date palm cultivation should be provided (92.91%), special training for the export of date palm should be organized (90.41%), training on value added products of dates should be given (89.58%) and training for improved date palm production technology should be increased (85.42%)

.Keywords: date palm production technology, date palm growers, constraints, suggestions

Introduction

Date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera L.*) is one of the oldest cultivated horticultural crops of the world, and its origin in Mesopotamia region of present-day Iraq during 4000 B.C. (Johnson *et al.*, 2013). It was a prominent tree of the desert oases and now, it is extensively cultivated with the help of irrigation facilities making it suitable for arid and semi-arid tract of the country. Over the years the crop has expanded its presence in more than 40 countries with its major concentration in Asia (Saudi Arabia, UAE, Iraq, Kuwait, Oman, Pakistan, Turkmenistan, Yemen *etc.*) and Africa (Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Mali, Morocco, Mauritania, Niger, Somalia, Sudan, Chad, Tunisia *etc.*). The pre-independence India was then among the major date palm producing countries in the world having its presence since the Mohenjodaro period (2000 B.C.) (Pareek *et al.*, 2021). In the Indus valley, the date palm was believed to be introduced by the soldiers of Alexander the Great during 4th century B.C. and further by Muslim invaders during 8th century A.D. Almost all the areas are now in the present-day Pakistan. The date groves of Kutch were the only area in India having natural date palm population which was believed to be introduced during 16th to 17th Century by traders, missionaries and Turk settlers visiting Arab countries. Most of these populations are of seedling origin.

In India, the commercial cultivation of date palm is rare. In Gujarat, Kutch district enjoys monopoly in the commercial cultivation of this crop. Date palm in the district is cultivated in 18825 hectares with the production of 178459 million tonnes. But, the average yield per plant per year in the district is low as compared to other date palm growing countries. Some constraints exist in the date palm orchards leading to low production of date palm. Taking in account this issue, a study was conducted to document the constraints

Results And Discussion

Constraints faced by the date palm growers in adoption of the date palm production technologies

Table 1: Constraints faced by the date palm growers in adoption of the date palm production technologies

(n = 240)

Sr. No.	Constraints	Frequency	Per cent	Rank
1	Lack of knowledge about improved variety	132	55.00	XIII
2	High price of good quality offshoots	161	67.08	IX
3	Unavailability of offshoots of improved variety	148	61.67	X
4	High price of tissue cultured plants	125	52.08	XIV
5	Lack of guidance about post harvest technology	137	57.08	XI
6	Unawareness about export system	208	86.67	II
7	High cost of plant protection equipments	36	15.00	XVIII

faced by the date palm growers of Kutch district and their suggestions to overcome the constraints in adoption of the date palm production technology

Objective

1. To study the constraints faced by the date palm growers in adoption of the date palm production technologies
2. To seek the suggestions of the date palm growers to overcome the constraints they faced in adoption of the date palm production technologies

Methodology

The present investigation was carried out in Kutch district of Gujarat. Out of ten talukas of Kutch district, four talukas viz., Mundra, Anjar, Mandavi and Bhuj talukas occupies more than 90 per cent of the total area under date palm cultivation in the district. Therefore, these four talukas were selected purposively. From each selected taluka, five date palm cultivating villages and from each selected village twelve date palm growers were selected randomly. Thus, total 240 date palm growers were selected as sample of the study. The data were collected by personal interview method with the help of structured interview schedule. For knowing constraints faced by the date palm growers in adoption of recommended date palm production technologies the date palm growers were asked to give the constraints actually faced by them. Later on the frequency and percentage of each constraint reported by the date palm growers were calculated and based on that rank was given to each constraint. The date palm growers were asked to give their valuable suggestions to overcome the constraints they faced. The responses were summed-up and converted into frequency and percentages. The rank was given to each suggestion.

8	High cost of insecticides/pesticides	41	17.08	XVII
9	Lack of knowledge about value added products of date palm	210	87.50	I
10	Unavailability of sufficient labour in time	84	35.00	XVI
11	Lack of timely and appropriate extension services	117	48.75	XV
12	High cost of transportation	197	82.08	V
13	Poor transport facility	136	56.67	XII
14	Higher charge of middle man	180	75.00	VII
15	Poor marketing facilities	192	80.00	VI
16	Non remunerative price	206	85.83	III
17	Complicated method for loan and subsidies	205	85.42	IV
18	Unawareness about various horticultural schemes	173	72.08	VIII

A critical look in the Table 1 indicates that the date palm growers faced eighteen constraints in adoption of date palm production technology. The important constraints faced by majority of the date palm growers in descending order of the importance were; lack of knowledge about value added products of date palm (87.50%), unawareness about export system (86.67%), non remunerative price (85.83%), complicated method for loan and subsidies (85.42%), high cost of transportation (82.08%), poor marketing facilities (80.00%), higher charge of middle man (75.00%), unawareness about various horticultural schemes (72.08%), high price of good quality offshoots (67.08%), unavailability of offshoots of improved variety (61.67%),

lack of guidance about post-harvest technology (57.08%), poor transport facility (56.67%), lack of knowledge about improved variety (55.00%), high price of tissue cultured plants (52.08%) and lack of timely and appropriate extension services (48.75%) which ranked first to fifteen, respectively. While, the other constraints reported by considerable number of the date palm growers were; unavailability of sufficient labour in time (35.00%), high cost of insecticides/pesticides (17.08%) and high cost of plant protection equipments (15.00%) ranked sixteen to eighteen, respectively. This finding is in the line with the findings of Ibupoto *et al.* (2015), Sumana (2017) and Narayanrao (2018).

Suggestions of the date palm growers to overcome the constraints they faced in adoption of the date palm production technologies

Table 2: Suggestions of the date palm growers to overcome the constraints they faced in adoption of the date palm production technologies

(n = 240)

Sr. No.	Suggestions	Frequency	Per cent	Rank
1	Literature about scientific methods of date palm cultivation should be provided	223	92.91	I
2	Date palm offshoots of improved variety and tissue cultured plants should be made available	175	72.92	IX
3	Training on value added products of dates should be given	215	89.58	III
4	Price of insecticides/pesticides should be low	199	82.92	V
5	Need to establish date palm co-operative society	160	66.67	XI
6	Sufficient organic fertilizers should be made available	188	78.33	VI
7	More extension work for horticultural scheme	167	69.58	X
8	Training for improved date palm production technology should be increased	205	85.42	IV
9	Facilities for field training should be increased	181	75.42	VII
10	Special training for the export of date palm should be organized.	217	90.41	II
11	Transportation support should be provided	178	74.17	VIII

A critical look in the Table 2 indicates that the date palm growers give eleven suggestions in adoption of date palm production technologies. The suggestions given by the date palm growers in descending order of the importance were; literature about scientific methods of date palm cultivation should be provided (92.91%), special training for the export of date palm should be organized (90.41%), training on value added products of dates should be given (89.58%), training for improved date palm production technology should be increased (85.42%), price of insecticides/pesticides should be low (82.92%), sufficient organic fertilizers should be made available (78.33%), facilities for field training should be increased (75.42%), transportation support should be provided (74.17%), date palm offshoots of improved variety and tissue cultured plants should be made available (72.92%), more extension work for horticultural scheme (69.58%) and need to establish date palm co-operative society (66.67%) were considered the major suggestions given by the date palm growers and ranked first to eleven, respectively. Similar finding was reported by Koli (2012), Ibupoto *et al.* (2015), Sumana (2017) and Narayanrao (2018).

Conclusion

The study has clearly brought out that the major constraints faced by the date palm growers were lack of knowledge about value added products of date palm, unawareness about export system, non remunerative price and complicated method for loan and subsidies. Major suggestions they provided were; literature about scientific methods of date palm cultivation should be provided, special training for the export of date palm should be organized, training on value added products of dates should be given and training for improved date palm production technology should be increased.

Conflict Of Interest

The authors of the paper declare no conflict of interest

References

1. **Ibupoto, S. A.; Maitlo, W. A. and Memon, S. A. (2015).** Assessment of the problems of date palm growers and their possible solutions at Khairpur. *Journal of Agricultural Technology*. **11**(4): 823-829.
2. **Johnson, D. V.; Al-Khayri, J. M. and Jain, S. M. (2013).** Seedling date plants (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) as genetic resources. *Emeritus Journal of Food and Agriculture*. **25**: 809-830.

3. **Koli, M. A. (2012).** Knowledge and adoption of coconut production technology in Junagadh district of Gujarat state. M.Sc. (Agri.) Thesis (Unpublished). Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh.
4. **Narayanrao, K. D. (2018).** Knowledge and adoption of farmers about pomegranate production practices in Saurashtra region. M.Sc. (Agri.) Thesis (Unpublished). Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh.
5. **Pareek, P. K.; Yadav, P. K.; Kumar, S.; Sarolia, D. K. and Sharma, B. D. (2021).** Integrated nutrients managements in Khadrawy date palm under hot arid region. *Indian Journal of Horticulture*. **77**(3): 450-455.
6. **Sumana, N. A. (2017).** Entrepreneurial behaviour and marketing practices of grape growers in Chikkaballapura district. M.Sc. (Agri.) Thesis (Unpublished). University of Agricultural Science, Bengaluru.